

Investigating Prescription Patterns, General Medicine, and Rational Drug Use in Orthopedic Outpatient Care

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Abstract:

Periodic evaluation of drug utilization is essential to enhance therapeutic effectiveness, minimize adverse effects, and ensure rational, cost-effective medical care. This study aimed to analyze prescribing patterns in the Orthopaedic Outpatient Department of a tertiary care hospital, focusing on patient demographics, prescription characteristics, commonly prescribed drug categories, and identifying deficiencies in prescribing practices. A total of 130 prescriptions were reviewed, revealing an average of 3.05 drugs per prescription, exceeding WHO's recommended limit and highlighting a concerning rate of polypharmacy (49.04%). The study also found that only 28.46% of drugs were prescribed by generic names, reflecting low adherence to cost-saving practices. Anti-ulcer drugs were the most frequently prescribed category (30.88%), often exceeding NSAID prescriptions, indicating possible overuse of gastro protective agents. Common documentation issues included missing doctor signatures (90.00%) and incomplete follow-up instructions (74.62%). These findings underscore the need for stricter adherence to WHO guidelines, increased use of generic drugs, and improved documentation practices. Interventions in these areas could significantly improve patient safety, reduce treatment costs, and enhance the quality of care in orthopaedic settings.

Keywords: Drug utilization, prescribing patterns, Orthopaedics, polypharmacy, generic prescribing, anti-ulcer drugs, WHO guidelines, prescription audit, rational drug use.

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Introduction

Periodic evaluation of drug utilization studies is essential as it enhances therapeutic effectiveness and minimizes adverse effects. Analyzing prescribing patterns is invaluable for monitoring, assessing, and providing structured feedback within healthcare systems, and it can guide medical practitioners in implementing beneficial adjustments. This process promotes rational, cost-effective medical care and contributes significantly to public health goals [1].

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines drug utilization studies as the exploration of the marketing, distribution, prescription, and consumption of drugs within a society, focusing on the medical, social, and economic outcomes [2]. This is particularly relevant in resource-limited settings like India, where the cost and accessibility of medications are critical factors in ensuring proper healthcare. Rational drug use thus becomes a priority [3].

Recognizing the importance of drug utilization studies, international organizations like the WHO and the International Network for Rational Use of Drugs (INRUD) have endorsed the development of standard indicators and data collection methodologies. These initiatives aim to promote rational drug use by providing benchmarks and tools for evaluation, ensuring improved health outcomes [4]. In fields such as orthopedics, the significance of prescribing patterns is amplified, given the common use of medications like non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and anti-ulcer agents, which are associated with potential adverse effects [5]. To support effective prescribing practices, WHO has established indicators that assess healthcare providers' performance. These indicators include:

Average number of drugs per encounter: Monitors polypharmacy levels, which are closely linked to adverse drug reactions.

Percentage of drugs prescribed by generic name: Tracks the use of generic drugs to help manage costs.

Percentage of encounters with antibiotics prescribed: Assesses antibiotic use, addressing concerns about overuse and resistance.

Percentage of encounters with injections prescribed: Evaluates the tendency to prescribe injectables, which can have serious health implications if overused.

Percentage of drugs prescribed from an essential drugs list or formulary: Measures adherence to national drug policies, promoting standardized care [6, 7].

Objectives

The objectives of the present study were as follows:

- To analyze the demographic characteristics of patients attending the Orthopaedic Outpatient Department (OPD).
- To assess the drug prescription profile for each reviewed prescription.
- To examine the commonly prescribed drug categories for orthopaedic outpatients.
- To calculate the average number of drugs prescribed per prescription.
- To identify the most frequently observed deficiencies in prescribing patterns.

Materials and Methods

Study Design

This research was structured as a prospective, observational study conducted in the Orthopaedic Department of a tertiary care teaching hospital.

Data Collection:

Data were collected and analyzed according to the study's objectives. Information gathered included patient demographics (age and sex), prescription details, the types and number of drugs prescribed, and issues identified within the prescriptions. Prescription-related issues were further categorized, examining factors such as whether the diagnosis was recorded, the presence of the prescriber's signature, the use of a doctor's stamp, proper notation of treatment duration, and clear follow-up instructions.

Result

The demographic analysis of patients reveals a diverse age distribution within the group of 130 individuals. The largest age groups are "Less than 12 years" and "18–60 years," each comprising 37 patients, which accounts for 28.46% of the total population for both groups.

The "12–18 years" group includes 23 patients, representing 17.69% of the sample, while the "More than 60 years" category encompasses 33 patients, or 25.39%.

This spread indicates a substantial presence of younger patients (under 12) and those in the general adult population (18–60), with fewer patients in the adolescent and senior age brackets.

Table 1: Patient Demographic Profile by Age Group

Sl. No	Age Distribution	Number	Percentage (%)
1	Less than 12 years	37	28.46
2	12 – 18 years	23	17.69
3	18 – 60 years	37	28.46
4	More than 60 years	33	25.39

The evaluation of prescription characteristics for 130 patients reveals several areas for improvement in prescribing practices. Notably, only 37 prescriptions (28.46%) utilized generic names, indicating limited adherence to cost-saving practices that could benefit patients financially. Additionally, only 14 prescriptions (10.77%) included more than one antibiotic, suggesting a cautious approach to antibiotic use, potentially beneficial for minimizing antibiotic resistance. A complete diagnosis was documented in 78 prescriptions (60%), showing moderate compliance with best practices; however, this leaves a significant portion without a fully documented

diagnosis, which may impact treatment accuracy and patient understanding. Follow-up instructions were provided in just 66 prescriptions (50.77%), meaning half of the patients did not receive clear guidance for their ongoing care. Prescription legibility, achieved in 89 cases (68.46%), represents a positive aspect, reducing the risk of medication errors due to unclear instructions. However, only 57 prescriptions (43.85%) included comprehensive details such as dose, route, strength, frequency, and dosage forms, which is a critical area requiring attention to enhance the safety and effectiveness of prescribed treatments.

Table 2: Detailed Profile of Prescription Characteristics

Sl. No	Parameters	Number of Prescriptions	Percentage (%)
1	Drugs prescribed by generic names	37	28.46
2	More than 1 antibiotic prescribed	14	10.77
3	Complete diagnosis written	78	60.0
4	Follow-up instructions provided	66	50.77
5	Prescription legibility	89	68.46
6	Completeness in terms of dose, route, strength, frequency, and dosage forms	57	43.85

The analysis of drug distribution among the 130 patients highlights the varying frequencies of different drug categories prescribed. Anti-ulcer drugs are the most commonly prescribed, accounting for 210 prescriptions (30.88%), reflecting a significant emphasis on managing gastric issues, likely due to the potential side effects of other medications like NSAIDs on the stomach lining.

NSAIDs, sometimes combined with Serratiopeptidase, make up 180 prescriptions (26.47%), indicating a high prevalence of pain and inflammation management in orthopaedic care. Multivitamins, minerals, and enzyme supplements were also frequently prescribed, with 160 prescriptions (23.53%), likely aimed at supporting

overall recovery and addressing deficiencies that may impact musculoskeletal health. Antibiotics accounted for 75 prescriptions (11.03%), signifying a careful approach to infection prevention or control without overuse, which aligns with prudent antibiotic stewardship. Finally, opioid analgesics were prescribed in 55 instances (8.09%), representing a smaller portion, possibly indicating cautious use of opioids for pain management due to concerns about dependency and side effects.

These findings suggest a balanced approach to addressing pain, inflammation, gastrointestinal health, and nutritional support, with anti-ulcer medications and NSAIDs being particularly prominent in orthopaedic care prescriptions.

Table 3: Distribution of Total Drugs Prescribed

Sl. No	Drug Category	Number of Drugs	Percentage of Total Drugs (%)
1	NSAIDs ± Serratiopeptidase	180	26.47
2	Opioid Analgesics	55	8.09
3	Antibiotics	75	11.03
4	Multivitamins, Minerals, and Enzymes	160	23.53
5	Anti-Ulcer Drugs	210	30.88

The analysis of prescription-related issues among 130 patients reveals several common problems that could impact the quality and clarity of patient care. Notably, the absence or illegibility of the doctor's signature was the most frequent issue, observed in 117 prescriptions (90.00%). This lack of clear identification can create challenges in verifying the prescriber and may lead to misunderstandings or accountability concerns. Additionally, the doctor's stamp was missing in 108 prescriptions (83.08%), further complicating the traceability of the prescription to a specific healthcare provider. Treatment duration, an essential element for effective medication management, was omitted in 73 prescriptions (56.15%), which could lead to patients inadvertently under- or overdosing. In 97

prescriptions (74.62%), follow-up instructions were either unclear or missing, potentially impacting patients' continuity of care and recovery outcomes. Furthermore, the diagnosis was not recorded in 52 prescriptions (40.00%), which is critical information for patients and other healthcare providers to understand the prescribed treatment's purpose and context. These results indicate key areas for improvement in prescription practices, particularly in ensuring clear identification of the prescriber, specifying treatment duration, and providing unambiguous follow-up instructions. Addressing these issues could enhance patient safety, continuity of care, and overall treatment efficacy.

Table 4: Common Issues Identified in Prescriptions

Sl. No	Description of Problem	Number of Prescriptions	Percentage (%)
1	Diagnosis not recorded	52	40.00
2	Doctor's signature absent or illegible	117	90.00
3	Doctor's stamp missing	108	83.08
4	Treatment duration not specified	73	56.15
5	Follow-up instructions unclear	97	74.62

Discussion

In any healthcare system, a fundamental priority is to ensure that patients receive the appropriate medication at the correct time and in the correct dosage. Adhering to the WHO's recommendations on rational drug use is pivotal in achieving this goal, as it provides guidance on safe, effective, and economical prescribing practices. Prescriptions are more than just instructions for medication—they reflect a physician's approach to treatment, their understanding of the disease, and the intended role of each medication. Prescription auditing has become essential in analyzing drug utilization patterns, serving as a tool for quality assurance in healthcare settings [8]. Data gathered through auditing can significantly benefit the healthcare sector and contribute to the formulation of effective drug policies.

In this study, 130 prescriptions were analyzed, showing a male predominance in the sample, with the majority of patients falling within the 18–60-year age group. An important parameter in studying drug utilization is the average number of drugs prescribed per encounter. WHO recommends limiting the number of drugs per prescription to less than three to minimize risks associated with polypharmacy [9]. However, the present study found an average of 3.05 drugs per prescription, which exceeds this recommendation. An increased number of drugs per prescription elevates the risk of adverse drug interactions, potentially exposes patients to a higher incidence of side effects, and escalates the financial burden on patients. Additionally, polypharmacy raises the probability of prescribing and dispensing errors, highlighting a need for stricter prescribing guidelines [8].

A concerning finding was that only 28.46% of drugs were prescribed by their generic names, a figure significantly lower than seen in similar studies within India, where generic prescribing has reached up to 73.4% [10]. This low percentage may reflect poorly on prescribers, who face criticism for potential undue influences from pharmaceutical companies. Prescribing medications by generic names is strongly recommended across the healthcare sector, and these results underscore the need for greater adherence to generic prescribing practices to enhance cost-effectiveness for patients.

Anti-ulcer drugs were the most frequently prescribed category, present in 30.88% of prescriptions. This was followed by NSAIDs (with or without Serratiopeptidase), which accounted for 26.47% of prescriptions. NSAIDs are commonly associated with gastrointestinal side effects, including a heightened risk of upper gastrointestinal complications [11-13]. Physicians often prescribe anti-ulcer medications as a protective measure against NSAID-induced gastric

issues. A study conducted in Japan observed that most orthopaedic practitioners routinely prescribe medications to mitigate NSAID-induced ulcers [14]. However, an interesting observation in this study is that anti-ulcer drugs were prescribed even more frequently than NSAIDs themselves, suggesting potential overuse or injudicious prescribing of gastroprotective medications, which may warrant closer evaluation. Polypharmacy was another critical issue identified, with 49.04% of prescriptions containing five or more medications. This rate of polypharmacy directly contravenes WHO guidelines, which advocate for a minimalistic approach to prescribing to avoid unnecessary drug interactions and adverse effects [9]. Addressing this high rate of polypharmacy requires implementing stricter protocols to align with recommended standards.

Several deficiencies were observed in the prescriptions analyzed. The most frequent issue was the absence of a legible or identifiable signature from the treating doctor, occurring in 90.00% of prescriptions. Additionally, the doctor's stamp, which serves as a further verification of the prescriber's identity, was absent in 83.08% of cases. Another concerning finding was that follow-up instructions were either unclear or missing in 74.62% of prescriptions, potentially hindering the continuity of care and reducing the effectiveness of treatment. Lastly, the diagnosis was not recorded in 40.00% of prescriptions, depriving patients and other healthcare providers of crucial information regarding the rationale for treatment.

These results reveal substantial gaps in prescription practices that, if addressed, could significantly improve patient outcomes. There is an urgent need for interventions aimed at enhancing prescription completeness, promoting generic prescribing, and reducing polypharmacy. Revision of current prescription practices, strict adherence to rational drug use principles, and regular prescription auditing are essential to advancing the quality, safety, and cost-effectiveness of patient care in the hospital setting.

Conclusion

This study highlights critical areas for improvement in prescribing practices within an orthopaedic department. Key findings include a high rate of polypharmacy (49.04%), limited generic prescribing (28.46%), and frequent use of anti-ulcer medications, sometimes exceeding NSAID prescriptions. Additionally, documentation issues, such as missing doctor signatures (90.00%) and incomplete follow-up instructions (74.62%), compromise prescription quality and patient care continuity.

Addressing these gaps requires strict adherence to WHO guidelines, increased generic prescribing,

and improved documentation practices. By implementing these changes through regular audits and provider education, the healthcare system can enhance patient safety, cost-effectiveness, and treatment outcomes, ultimately advancing overall care quality.

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